

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF THE FORMATION OF STUDY COMPETENCIES REGARDING ART LITERACY IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article provides information on the formation of educational competencies related to visual literacy in students, educational components that are its components, pedagogical skills and types of pedagogical techniques. Also, the important importance of the formation of visual literacy educational competences in the social development of the society was analyzed.*

Keywords: *creative abilities of students of general secondary education in relation to pictorial activities, folk, decorative and practical art and design language, drawing and pictorial models in design and media art, art-media tools, artistic and practical crafts, norm and harmony, competence.*

Step-by-step development of visual activity in the world education system, ensuring the coherence and continuity of the processes of prospective formation of students' artistic creativity, teaching visual, folk, decorative-practical art and design language, developing children's aesthetic competence. The purposeful use of social stories and conversations is of particular importance. Also, forming design thinking in students through the systematization of creative, improvisational and problematic tasks in visual arts classes, harmonizing individual and collective forms of independent educational and creative activities, project education, artistic and didactic teaching improving the methodology of using modern technologies is especially important. In the world, a number of scientific researches are being carried out on the development of a didactic system for the formation of basic, metasubject, artistic-aesthetic, general cultural competences of students in visual art classes, and on improving the methodical foundations of teaching visual art using interactive software tools. In particular, in the process of teaching art-related subjects, it is important to cultivate visual literacy, use graphic models in design and media art, use information and communication technologies, develop critical and creative thinking, ethical skills, personal and social, intercultural competence in students. becomes important. At the same time, the development of life skills through the use of art-media tools and technologies in visual art classes, the formation of patriotism and civic competences in students based on artistic education requires the implementation of creative activities on the basis of prioritizing vitagen education. is enough.

In our republic, great importance is attached to the improvement of visual arts education based on innovative approaches, the wide introduction of interactive and digital technologies of teaching. Developing advanced methods of teaching while preserving the traditions of "master-student" and art education, and implementing the activities of creative workshops in the educational process, in the areas of visual arts (table, graphic, majestic, miniature, sculpting) to

select talented artists, to improve their aesthetic level and skills" is becoming a special priority. This requires the improvement of didactic requirements for the formation of visual literacy educational competencies in students, the development of the model and didactic conditions for the implementation of this process[1].

The educational, educational goals and tasks set in the course of teaching fine arts provide students with comprehensive aesthetic education by means of educational materials related to fine and applied art, design, artistic and practical crafts, and architecture. It is to form and develop their artistic and visual intellectual potentials and to develop their creative competences. In the process of completing educational tasks related to learning the basics of fine art, students are directed to creativity. Through new solutions to problems, students improve their creativity and imagination, the skills of effective use of rules of fine art, such as norms and harmony, in their visual creative activities.

Creative artistic thinking gives rise to completely new ideas and imaginations, creates the ground for the realization of abilities and opportunities, individuality hidden in a person. Such qualities are important not only for scientists, but for professionals working in all fields. Formation and development of educational competencies related to visual literacy in students creates motivation for creative thinking in them. As a result, new elements of creative thinking are formed in students, creative ideas and imaginations are enriched, and a great ground is created for the realization of their hidden visual creative abilities and opportunities. That is why the development of thinking and visual creativity is considered one of the main tasks in the educational system. From this point of view, it is based on the fact that visual art classes have more opportunities among other subjects in developing visual creative thinking of students in general secondary education schools. This opportunity, without a doubt, is realized only with competence. In this sense, the formation of educational competencies of students in the field of visual arts, as well as subjects that develop creativity in students, is a unique pedagogical guarantee of educating a creative person who thinks creatively in the future.

As one of the important directions of reforming the education system in today's new Uzbekistan, which is developing in line with the times, in particular, the subject of "Art" taught in general secondary schools, first of all, special attention is paid to the formation of educational competences in the field of students. After all, in the state social policy of our republic, special attention is paid to individual interests and the priority of education, to the rich national values, cultural-historical traditions and intellectual heritage of our people, and in the process of integrating Uzbekistan into the world community, it is an important factor to educate a creative generation who thinks creatively. These factors mean that the use of educational and educational possibilities of visual arts is of great importance.

Formation and development of educational competences for students in the field is the priority direction of developing the "Art" lessons taught in general secondary schools today in accordance with the social development of the society, in this regard, in order to modernize the teaching system and content of the "Fine Art" lesson, to improve the science programs, the mechanisms of modern approach to the educational process, the main driving force of these reforms in the process of modernizing the educational system is the purposeful use of new modern pedagogical technologies should be put into practice. The main idea of these educational activities is, without a doubt, to form and develop academic competences in the field in the learners.

At the same time, it is worth noting that a comprehensive approach to the development of students' educational competencies related to visual literacy in visual art classes is also important.

On the basis of studying the historical foundations of fine art, observing the illustrations drawn on works of art, students can learn about the lifestyle, culture, clothing, tools, animals, structure, shape, color, and texture of our ancestors who lived thousands of years ago. They will have a broad idea about the dimensions and their mutual relations. The application of these ideas to practical pictorial-creative activities is important as an important component of students' educational competencies related to pictorial literacy.

The image is processed on the basis of variability, combination, etc. Students consciously master the theoretical foundations of fine art - light and shadow, color theory, perspective, composition, and apply them in their visual and creative activities. They take a creative approach to the pictures they draw and try to have a new, original content. Also, one of the important tasks of visual arts classes is to develop students' observation, to be able to see and feel the existence, as well as to develop memory. Therefore, in this matter, i.e., these qualities formed in students should be considered as one of the important components of educational competencies related to visual literacy.

The incomparably rich cultural and spiritual heritage created by the Uzbek people must be taken as a basis in the content of the fine arts curriculum. Therefore, it is necessary to teach the world-famous historical national architecture, visual and folk art works of the Uzbek people in general secondary education schools more widely and more deeply than other materials. At the same time, it is desirable to differentiate the content of education in general secondary schools by regions and cities. Because the history and development of applied art and architecture in the regions, cities, and even villages of Uzbekistan is unique. This can be clearly seen in the practical arts and artistic crafts of Bukhara, Samarkand, Kattakurgan, Rishton, Shahrisabz, Nurota, Margilan, Gijduvan, Urgut, Khujaili and other cities. So, it can be concluded that as structural components of students' visual literacy educational competencies, there should be knowledge of architecture, applied decorative arts, and artistic crafts.

Teaching students to perceive the subtle beauties of nature, art and life by heart as one of the factors of the formation of important components of educational competencies related to visual literacy in general secondary school students, their recognition of such factors as having a clear idea of the theoretical and practical bases and practical requirements of procedures in order to consciously follow the theoretical and practical rules of visual art in their visual and creative activities, thus expanding the range of artistic and visual thinking of students can be achieved. It is known that the growth of visual and artistic aesthetic feeling in students directly leads to the formation of the skills of aesthetic assessment of the properties of objects and events. In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to the perception of colors in nature when educating students' pictorial-artistic aesthetic perception. Because it is impossible to imagine the formation of educational competencies related to visual literacy without knowledge of color science.

Today, a new, original form of didactic design aimed at the formation of educational competencies related to visual literacy in students of visual arts is being created, according to which the educational standard is studied as a didactic design tool. Analysis is required. This situation has arisen as a social order of the state, and it is organized on the basis of new complex didactic projects aimed at the formation of students' artistic and visual thinking and educational competencies related to the field. They take into account both visual creative activity of students

and recall activity in an optimal way. Didactic design according to the interrelationship of the educational and cognitive activity of students and the components of social experience:

- projecting knowledge, ideas, views;
- designing skills;
- designing experience of creative activity;
- relationships can be divided into such as design.

For example, in the course of the lesson, the teacher shows to the students a new branch of a tree that has sprouted branches and leaves, and explains that the color of the leaves of a young plant is light green and delicate. In the autumn season, it means that the leaves of the tree are naturally golden, that is, they are in yellow and red colors, and the rustling "talking" of the fallen leaves is figurative. In their visual activities and drawings, students describe, for example, houses, trees, birds, animals, people, vehicles. From this, they correctly interpret the events, events, spaces, objects and objects described without words according to their dimensions, proportions, textures, shapes, colors and colors, and they are compositionally correct in their pictorial activities. they try to place. This means that, along with thinking about the proportionality, perfection, appropriateness of their structure, important components of educational competencies related to visual literacy are formed and developed in students.

Special attention should be paid to the content and quality of the educational material presented in the formation of students' theoretical knowledge and practical educational competencies in fine arts classes. It is known that Ya.A.Komensky used the term[2] "learning material" for the first time in his work "Great Didactics" and said: "Education is to familiarize students with learning material". According to him, education consists of three parts; teacher, student and learning material:

- teacher - knowledge giver;
- the student perceives knowledge;
- educational material is the movement of knowledge from the teacher to the children.

So, based on the thesis that information content is materialized in educational materials in the subject of "Art", comprehensive pedagogical processing of the information content, management of the processes of competence formation in students, the selection of educational materials by students requires adaptation to the possibilities of real knowledge. In this way, choosing the optimal content and methodology of educational materials and information, which ensure the formation of academic competences in the field in the educational process, increases the possibilities of improving the effectiveness and quality of education.

It should be acknowledged that the Uzbek people have spread the word to the whole world with their ancient pictorial, practical, historical architectural art and culture. In Uzbekistan, in the centuries before Christ, the types of visual arts such as painting, sculpture, and unique styles of architectural art were extremely developed, some examples of which are Varakhsha, Afrosiyob, Tuproq kala, Ayrtom, Dalvarzin tepa, Fayoz tepa, Halchayon, Teshik Qala and a number of other places can be a vivid example of this. The artistry of these 5-6 thousand-year-old works of art is almost no different from the examples of rare works of art created by contemporary artists and sculptors.

If we look at the period, culture, science, art and literature developed and progressed in the direction of Islamic culture in Movoraunnahr in the 9th-12th centuries. During this period, Ahmad al-Farghani, Musa al-Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Imam

Ismail al-Bukhari, al-Tirmizi, Abu Abdullah Rudaki, Abdul Qasim Firdawsi, Ahmad Yassavi, Mahmud Kashgari, Mahmud Zamakhshari, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Najmuddin Kubro lived and created hundreds of virtues. The rich heritage left by these unique geniuses - stars of world culture to future generations has not lost its importance. Philosophical and aesthetic views of these great figures are formed in the form of teachings such as "Ahl dil", "Ilmi Hayrat", "Ilmi Hal" and "Qol" and are of great importance in the observation of existence and evaluation of visual and practical works of art.

A pedagogue is considered the main participant of school education, including the designer of the educational process aimed at improving the methodical system of developing educational competencies in students, and the one who implements it, and fulfills the important social (state) order of training a highly qualified specialist. What will be the role of the teacher in the pedagogical system?

1. The teacher must clearly and clearly define the goal of education in accordance with the social order of the state, so that it is possible to draw a conclusion about the design and implementation of the didactic process that ensures the achievement of the goal within the allotted time. Let's go.

2. When selecting the content of the educational process that corresponds to the specified educational goal, the teacher must ensure that the educational content of the subject, which ensures the improvement and development of the competencies of the students in a certain way, is compatible with the level of its mastery by the students must be taken into account.

3. The teacher should be familiar with the requirements of the didactic process as structural elements of the pedagogical system, which is the basis for improving the methodological system of formation of educational competencies in the field in the students, and choose the most suitable options for each subject of the lesson. must design independently.

4. It is necessary for the teacher to be able to use effective forms of teaching in the implementation of the didactic process related to the improvement of educational competencies in students.

5. The teacher should control the extent to which the student, who is a participant of the pedagogical system, acquires the educational content, i.e., the methodical system aimed at the formation of educational competencies in students, with the most optimal methods of education. The obtained information provides an opportunity to manage the pedagogical system in an appropriate manner or determines the content of which element in the methodological system needs to be corrected.

In conclusion, on the basis of the above-mentioned opinions, it can be considered that the formation of educational competencies related to visual literacy in students is carried out in the following directions:

- it is necessary to clarify the issues of enriching its content and directions and the prospects of expansion within the framework of students' interest in artistic and creative activities;
- in the process of formation of educational competencies related to visual literacy, it is necessary to take into account certain factors, conditions and ways of stimulation in the process of activating students' interest in artistic visual activity.

These factors and conditions include:

- arousing various motives that arouse their interest in artistic and creative activities, developing complexes that expand the prospects for the development of the field of visual arts;
- preparation of specific instructions for students to determine the necessary goals for improving personal qualities and skills related to visual activity;
- within the scope of students' interest in artistic and visual activities, to determine the prospects of expanding its contents and directions while enriching them;
- in the process of forming educational competencies related to visual literacy, in order to ensure the direction of students' aesthetic needs and the development of their high emotional-creative-artistic taste, with the methods, styles and means of satisfying their interest in visual arts (various it is necessary to work with sources, work with various information, including information on computer literacy, etc.);
- to direct students to emotional-emotional and artistic analytical perception in their chosen artistic activities (for example, visual, applied art) in order to satisfy their artistic-aesthetic interest in the works of art created by artists, to have a valuable attitude towards say;
- in order to "communicate" with the masterpieces of fine art, to satisfy their interest in them, to acquire independent knowledge and improve their independent work, to activate educational and propaganda activities, to plan and systematically organize all kinds of round-conversations with the student community transfer.

REFERENCES

1. Абдулла Авлоний. Туркий Гулистон ёхуд ахлоқ. – Т.: 1994. – 296 б.
2. Ибрагимов Х.И., Абдуллаева Ш.А. Педагогика. Ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: Фан, 2004. – 182 б.
3. Сулаймонов А., Абдуллаев Н. Тасвирий санъат. 7-синф ўқувчилари учун дарслик. – Т.: Фафур Фулом номидаги НМИУ, 2014. – 80 б.
4. Ҳасанов Р. Мактабда тасвирий санъатни ўқитиш методикаси. – Т.: “Фан”, 2004. – 106 б.
5. Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси № 1. – Т.: “Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси” давлат илмий нашриёти, 2000. – 496 б.
6. Сулаймонов А. Художественное образование старшеклассников на занятиях книжной графикой. Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата педагогических наук. – М.: 1992. – 16 с.
7. Абдуллаев С.Ф. Восточная миниатюра в системе высшего художественно-педагогического образования: Автореф. дис. док.пед.наук. – М.: МПГУ. 1996. – 34 с.
8. Шавдиров, С. А. (2017). Подготовка будущих учителей к исследовательской деятельности. Педагогическое образование и наука, (2), 109-110.
9. Shovdirov, S. BB Boymetov Methods of Organizing Practical and Theoretical Classes for Students in The Process of Teaching Fine Arts International Journal on Integrated Education.
10. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // Science, education and culture. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
11. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.

12. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." *International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education* 1 (2020): 6-15.
13. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
14. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –T., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.
15. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
16. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
17. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." *Вопросы науки и образования* 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
18. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
19. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
20. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).